

Investigation of Prebiotic Components Used for the Development of Health-Promoting Products

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a.) Instrumental Analytical Examination of the Carbohydrate Spectrum of Prebiotics Used in Product Development and the Created Honey-Based Products.

Additionally, the monitoring of qualitative parameters of polysaccharide molecules and transformation processes during processing, considering industrial conditions.

b.) Analysis of the Effectiveness of Product Components with Prebiotic Effects Using Microbiological and Molecular Biological Methods.

The prebiotic index, the degree of substrate assimilation, growth rate, total short-chain fatty acid content, and synbiotic properties will be determined.

Substances Containing Prebiotics and Their Effects on Body Functions

Fructans

Fructans are naturally occurring oligosaccharides found in milligram amounts in foods such as onions, bananas, wheat, artichokes, garlic, and others (Chow, 2002). They are extracted from chicory or produced from sucrose in the food industry. Despite their similarities, fructans differ in terms of origin, structure, and fermentation (Douglas & Sanders, 2008). In vitro studies are not sufficient to qualify a substance as a prebiotic or to support claims of effectiveness, as these methods cannot fully model the dynamic nature of colonic metabolism. There are methodological limitations that include the metabolism of resident microflora. These factors contribute to variations in measurable colony-forming bacterial counts, as well as in the concentrations of short-chain fatty acids, enzymes, and other values (Blaut, 2002). Several factors may interfere with results, including the chemical composition of the proposed prebiotic, its fermentation profile, the study design, the baseline distribution of colonic microbiota in subjects, the methods used to observe effects within a given subgroup, and the statistical models applied to interpret the data (Scholz-Ahrens et al., 2001).

Resistant Starch

Non-fructan prebiotics can also be examined for their fermentation characteristics, prebiotic properties, and health effects. Resistant starch has been the subject of numerous studies documenting its prebiotic effects, both as a single component and in combination with fructo-oligosaccharides. Resistant starch is found in raw potatoes, cooked and cooled starchy foods ("retrograded" starch), and unripe fruits such as bananas. It is also present in many commercially available food products due to its processability (Douglas & Sanders, 2008). Resistant starch is specifically manufactured for food industry applications. The standard dose of resistant starch is approximately 20 g/day, but due to the diverse fermentation profiles of prebiotic components, even low doses of 2.5 to 5 g/day have shown prebiotic effects. Many bread and cereal products contain significant amounts of resistant starch or inulin-type compounds to increase fiber content or reduce energy content. A daily intake of 20 g of resistant starch appears to be the minimum healthy dose (Cassidy et al., 1994). Bounik et al. (2004) found that short-chain fructo-oligosaccharides, soy oligosaccharides, galacto-oligosaccharides,

and type III resistant starch significantly increased the number of *Bifidobacterium* species in stool within 7 days at a dosage range of 2.5–5 g/day. It is important to validate markers that predict health benefits in humans. However, this is a challenging process, as mechanistic and epidemiological studies are also necessary for validation. One major obstacle in developing biomarkers for the study of probiotics and prebiotics is the incomplete mapping of the human gut microbiota, making it difficult to fully interpret the presence, absence, or concentration of various genera, species, or strains.

Examined Materials	Prebiotic Index Control		Technological Effect
	Without Digestion	With Digestion	Without Digestion
Analytically Pure Prebiotics			
Chicory inulin (Fluka)	2.72	2.53	4.11
Chicory fructo-oligosaccharide (Sigma)	2.67	2.40	3.22
Dahlia tuber inulin (Fluka)	2.59	2.42	3.54
Dahlia tuber inulin (Sigma)	2.68	2.72	3.17
Lactulose (Fluka)	2.36	2.88	3.60
Raffinose	2.48	2.76	3.44
Commercially Available Prebiotic Products			
Frutafit HD (inulin)	2.73	2.33	3.43
Frutafit CLR (inulin)	2.43	2.73	3.44
Fructan syrup (fructo-oligosaccharide)	2.22	2.23	4.80
Synergy GR (inulin)	2.47	2.76	3.60
Synergy 1 (inulin)	2.70	2.66	2.94
Resistant Starch Commercial Products			
Hi-maize	2.38	2.49	2.45
Novelose	2.73	2.77	2.80
Ultratex	2.21	2.81	2.52
Thermflo	2.40	2.71	2.75
Processed Natural Materials and Extracts			
Elderberry extract	1.28	1.27	1.62
Chicory meal	1.67	1.59	1.26
Jerusalem artichoke flour	1.36	1.70	1.36
Jerusalem artichoke jam	1.42	1.65	1.78
Sea buckthorn berry extract	1.79	1.56	1.67
Cherry extract	1.45	1.63	1.55

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